

Analysis of the Artistic Healing Effect and Installation Value of Bronzes Unearthed in the State of Chu

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ABSTRACT

Bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu are the most numerous in archaeology, and there are significant differences in the production process, shape and material of bronzes in the early and late stages of the State of Chu. Therefore, this paper analyzes the characteristics of bronzes in Chu State, compares and analyzes the dings and prohibitions, and studies the dragon pattern devices, mechanical balance, metallurgical materials, and the artistic healing effect and decorative art value of bronzes. The results show that the decorative patterns of bronzes unearthed in Chu are balanced and countermeasures; the deviation between the centre and centre of gravity points is slight. The metallurgical material contains brass, iron oxide, and other materials with good toughness and rigidity and can provide a basis for complex decoration. At the same time, the bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu play a role in psychological hinting and psychological healing in shape and structure and have high installation art value for modern art design. Therefore, analyzing the artistic healing effect of bronzes unearthed in the Chu State and researching the value of installation art can provide inspiration and reference for archaeological research.

Keywords: State of Chu, Unearthed Bronzes, Artistic Healing, Installation, Artistic Value.

INTRODUCTION

Bronze ware is a brilliant pearl in the art of the Chu State, and the people of Chu have created countless exquisite bronze artworks for the land of China with rich imagination, nimble hands and outstanding skills. Chu bronzes have always been famous for their originality, chicness (Bi, Yang, Du, Tang, & Luo, 2023), richness, and ingenuity, representing the ancient decorative arts of China. The bronze smelting and casting technology unearthed in the State of Chu is first-class and has attracted the world's attention today (Martín Bravo & Sanabria Marcos, 2023). The state of Chu was first established at the beginning of the late Shang Dynasty. Due to low productivity, Chu bronzes have not yet developed. With the continuous increase of the national strength of the State of Chu and the improvement of productivity (Elgart-Sharon et al., 2023), the bronze ware of the State of Chu has developed rapidly. At that time, the State of Chu formed a unique aesthetic style. Chu bronzes form a unique system, unique shapes, and increasingly improved casting skills. Influenced by the geometric ornaments of the Western Zhou Dynasty (Ge, Lu, Dou, Li, & Liu, 2023), bronze ornaments unearthed in the State of Chu show a regular arrangement style. However, the Chu bronzes innovated vigorously and gradually formed a unique Chu style, such as carving, relief, casting, inlay, etc., all representing the pinnacle of ancient bronze casting technology. Therefore, this paper researches bronzes unearthed in the Chu State, analyzes their artistic healing effects, and discusses the value of installation art to support archaeological research on bronzes (Güder, Özdemir, & Verčík, 2023).

AN OVERVIEW OF BRONZES UNEARTHED IN THE STATE OF CHU

Cultural Integration of Bronzes Unearthed in the State of Chu

If we talk about the cultural history of the Chinese Bronze Age, it is natural to relate to the history of the Chu state. The history of the State of Chu represents the history of bronze development in ancient southern China. Suppose we want to study the cultural development of bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu. In that case, it is necessary to analyze its social background and the reasons for its development and conduct detailed discussions. According to the content recorded in the "Shiji Chu Shijia", "When King Wen of Zhou, there was a Miao descendant named Xiongxiang (Kiernan & Henz, 2023), and his son was serving as King Wen of Zhou at that time, and then experienced a descendant Xiong Yi, who became the king of Zhou, and soon Xiong Yi was sealed by King Zhou Cheng to the land of Chu barbarians for many reasons." According to the "Zuo Chuan Zhao Gong 12th Year" (J. Li et al., 2023), it is recorded: "In the past, my ancestor King Xiong was in Jingshan, and the blue strands of the road were reckless, and the mountains and forests were trekking to the Son of Heaven. It can be seen from this that during the initial development period of the Chu state, productivity was particularly low, and the social form was primitive, mainly using the culture of the Zhou Dynasty (Q. Li et al., 2023). In addition, the territory of Chu was still extremely small and cramped, so it was also culturally influenced by the Zhou Dynasty. The original bronzes of the State of Chu still did not form an independent modelling style, nor did they have a self-consistent ornamental style. During the "Hanyang Zhuji" period, the Zhou Dynasty tried to weaken the state of Chu. Chu bronzes lagged in many aspects, such as smelting and casting technology ornamentation (S. Li, X. Li, Zhu, & Y. Li, 2023), engraving, etc. As the Zhou dynasty lost its political control and its military power waned, the state of Chu vigorously developed bronze. During the period when King Zhuang of Chu went north, the metallurgical technology of bronzes in the State of Chu developed significantly. Through the efforts of many Chu monarchs, the state of Chu gradually annexed dozens of countries in the middle and upper reaches of the Jianghan and Huai rivers, and its bronze production process became increasingly unique. It can be seen from this that the bronzes of the Chu State have multi-ethnic integration, rich in multi-regional cultural characteristics, and have artistic healing.

Characteristics of Bronzes Unearthed in the State of Chu

Bronzes unearthed in China have these characteristics: "many", that is, many quantities and types; "special", that is, the shape is often extremely unique and rich in Chu cultural color; "high", that is, significant weight, large volume, and high quality; "fine", that is, exquisite beauty, ingenious craftsmanship; and "sharp", that is, quality skills are among the cutting-edge. For example, the Chu bronzes that have been unearthed so far show the characteristics of a large number, and the size and weight are large, and they all show a sense of height and majesty from near and far, which is amazing. At the beginning of the founding of the Chu state, bronze was not comparable to bronze in other regions in terms of appearance, artistry and casting technology. However, with the development of the Spring and Autumn Warring States period, the national strength of the Chu State and the integration of various cultures, the artistic aesthetic of bronze changed. The bronzes of the State of Chu became romantic because of the Chu culture. In the middle and late period of the Chu State, bronzes were reflected in the casting and surface decoration techniques, and the metallurgical technology also reached a very high level. Chu bronzes have successively used various decorative techniques, such as casting and setting red copper, engraved lines, gilt, wrong gold and silver inlays, etc., all of which add charm to bronzes. They are also different from the bronze decorations of the Shang and Zhou Dynasties, and their artistic value has also peaked.

The Artistic Healing of Chu Bronzes

Art healing first appeared in the United States in the 50s and 60s of the last century and then gradually spread to Asia, mainly for the psychological healing of the viewer. In clinical research, the treatment method of art intervention has become the main psychotherapy method, so art as a healing method is widely used in psychotherapy in European and American countries. Bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu combine psychological theory with the visuality of art and the rich creativity of art and carry out clinical psychotherapy for appreciation. Art healing is a method of expressive healing of people's psychology. Art creation and appreciation of artworks change the participants' physiological and mental state and improve their emotional well-being. As we all know, art has a specific healing power and can help people relieve unhappiness and psychological discomfort in their hearts (X. Li et al., 2023).

In recent years, the study of artistic healing of unearthed ancient cultural relics has become a trend, and people in psychology have also recognized the role of artistic healing. The bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu can be used as a psychological counselling and treatment method and help people relieve negative emotions in different ways to relax their mood and produce a more positive self-value identity. The healing effect of art attaches importance to the edification of art on people. It can better avoid people's self-protection mechanism

through subtle cultural and artistic edification so that people can unconsciously gradually integrate into artistic creation, soothe the body and mind, and enable people to express their true feelings, laying a good foundation for subsequent spiritual healing. In addition, for people with insufficient cognitive ability and lack of language expression potential, it is difficult to use language to express their emotional experience, and they can use art healing to express the true feelings in their hearts to achieve the purpose of effectively healing the heart (Ma, Wu, & Yan, 2023).

The Role of Installation Art in Bronzes Unearthed in the State of Chu

Installation art, still extremely foreign to many, was born in the sixties of the last century. Installation art is a very open and free art form with strong inclusiveness. Installation art allows people to "open their minds" to free artistic expression in the sense of space. One of the more famous early installations was 1917's *Springs* (Duchamp), a ready-made men's ceramic urinal that Duchamp bought on the market. Duchamp's sending the finished product to the exhibition as a work of art was a provocation, so it had a subversive significance that influenced the art world of the 20th century. Thanks to Duchamp's event, installation art developed and became a manifestation of breaking through constraints rather than being limited to traditional sculpture (Mamatsis et al., 2023). Later, art forms in painting, architecture, music, and other fields can become one of the elements of installation art, expanding the boundaries of installation art, enriching the creative methods of installation art, and making it more accessible. In the era of science and technology, bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu have also become a kind of installation art. The forms of creation have become more and more diversified (Murat, 2023). People have been able to easily use interactive multimedia to obtain installation art and continue to bring innovative forms for this, so installation art has long been dynamic and diverse. At present, bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu are often associated with installation art and displayed in their setting places (Peng, 2023).

ANALYSIS OF THE ARTISTIC HEALING EFFECT OF BRONZES UNEARTHED IN THE STATE OF CHU

During the Spring and Autumn Warring States period, the State of Chu was a superpower with a rich and powerful country and a vast territory, and once dominated the four directions. At the spiritual and cultural level, the culture of the Chu state is inclusive, and through the annexation of small neighboring countries, Chu once absorbed many different cultures, and formed a unique Chu culture after integrating the essence of the culture of each small country. In material culture, bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu have always developed into a separate series because of their unique shape characteristics (Turkteki, 2023), and reached the peak of ancient bronze art with their majestic posture and exquisite casting techniques. The bronzes of the State of Chu use unique smelting technology and casting technology, and although they inherit the foundation of Zhou culture, they have formed a unique Chu style in subsequent development. The casting process is extremely complex (Yang et al., 2023), and the bronzes cast are unmatched by any princely state except the pre-Qin era. As far as the artistic style is concerned, the bronzes unearthed in the Chu State are gorgeous, exaggerated and exquisite, and they also reflect the strong aesthetic awareness and imagination of the Chu people. Due to the large number of bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu and the limited space of this article (Zhang et al., 2023), in order to better analyze the artistic healing effect of the bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu, the author will take the bronzes of the State of Chu unearthed in Weichuan as an example to discuss in detail. The author believes that the artistic healing effect of bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu has these aspects.

The Shape Plays a Tranquil Psychological Suggestive Role

In the long history of the long river, the beauty of Chu bronzes has always left a certain position in the minds of the Chinese people, whether it is middle school students, college students, or young people entering the society, all kinds of people in the society, through quality education, cultural education, social life and other ways, to gradually understand and understand Chu bronzes, and understand their status in the history of ancient Chinese artifacts, and understand their humanistic and artistic value as treasures of ancient bronzes. And this impression rooted in the hearts of the Chinese people often makes the Chinese people feel a sense of pride. Therefore, whenever it comes to the treasures of the Spring and Autumn and Warring States periods in China, the bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu will always come to the minds of many people, and if they are talkers, it is easy to be proud of this and discuss it with great enthusiasm, and then show their breadth of knowledge and outstanding taste, followed by the "envious" eyes cast by others. Therefore, people can obtain psychological satisfaction through the appreciation of bronzes unearthed in the Chu State, through the appreciation and sharing of their artistry and uniqueness, aesthetic connotation, etc., and increase self-confidence, improve personal comprehensive ability, obtain psychological balance, and promote their mental health development. In addition, the continuous appreciation and evaluation of the uniqueness, artistry, shape and other aspects of the bronzes unearthed in the Chu State will also allow people to establish a good image in the eyes of others, and then reduce

some contradictions and psychological frustrations in interpersonal relationships. Even people who have no knowledge or understanding of the bronzes unearthed in the Chu State can gradually feel the power of a pleasant mood from the beauty of shape, ornamentation, and craftsmanship of the Chu bronzes, thus bringing spiritual artistic healing, as shown in Figure 1.

Early Chu State

Late Chu State

Figure 1. Bronzes Unearthed in the State of Chu

Figure 1 shows that the shape of the bronze excavated in the State of Chu presents a shape of width and narrowness, giving people a hint of vigor, and the shape structure is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Changes in the Shape of Bronzes Excavated in the State of Chu

It can be seen from Figure 2 that the shape of the bronzes unearthed in the Chu State shows a trend of change from bottom to top and from inside to outside in terms of line changes, giving people a positive psychological hint. At this time, the bronzes of the State of Chu not only have the characteristics of the Western Zhou, but also show the characteristics of streamlined and hollow shape, giving people an atmospheric, magnificent and broad feeling, which makes people happy and convinced.

Decorative Patterns Cultivate People's Interest

Psychological research has shown that at the moment when people are in a very happy mood, the human body will release "libido" substance, which is an instinctive substance, which can effectively stimulate the human brain and greatly enhance people's psychological stress resistance. Because the history of Chu bronzes has a long history, therefore, its cultural value, artistic value and other aspects of value are very high, even people who have no understanding of this, but also have a certain respect and appreciation for this, and they also hope to take advantage of the appreciation of Chu bronzes, to improve taste, so as to comfort the personal heart, is to see the process of watching the bronzes unearthed in the Chu State is a kind of healing of people's hearts, can make people feel calm, feel gentle, thereby healing people's hearts, such as, In the Chu bronzes excavated in Weichuan, there is an open-cut moire copper forbidden, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Open-Cut Moire Copper Forbidden

The open-cut moire copper in Figure 3 was forbidden to be stored in the Henan Museum and was unearthed in 1978 in Tomb No. 2 of Xiasi in Weichuan County. Cast in the late Spring and Autumn period, the pass is 28.8 cm high, 125.5 cm long and 67.6 cm wide, and the full ban is cuboidal. In the middle of the forbidden surface, a rectangular plane is shown for storing objects, while the four sides and sides of the forbidden surface are intertwined by three layers of copper stems of different thicknesses, and are carved in the shape of clouds. There are 12 three-dimensional dragon-shaped ornaments attached to this forbidden perimeter, and the dragon horns and dragon tail are used as open-cut decorations, because of the open mouth and tongue, concave waist, and the tail is rolled up and the front paws climb the forbidden edge, so it is quite lively and very ornamental, and its hind paws are tightly grasping the forbidden outer wall, so it is more dynamic and handsome. And the four corners of the forbidden bottom and around it are 12 monsters, all of which are instrumental feet, the dragon beast is straight chest, concave waist and tail, and has the forefoot forward extension, so only a tubular foot can support its body, and then more show the forbidden casting exquisite, shape and decoration magnificent, if someone can watch it at the scene, it can delight the soul, and experience the craftsmanship of bronze unearthed in the Chu Kingdom, deepen personal pleasure, let the psychology obtain satisfaction, and achieve the purpose of peace of mind, meditation and pleasure. For the balanced comparison of open-cut moire copper prohibition, the results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Equilibrium Ratio of Open-Cut Moire Copper Forbidden

Center Point Position (M)	Center of Gravity Position(m)	Number of Dragon Ornaments (pcs)	Front and Rear center Point Position (m)	Front and Rear Center of Gravity Position (m)
62.52	61.23	12	32.12	31.24
Left and Right Deviation = 1.23			Before and after deviation = 1.11	

It can be seen from Table 1 that the balance of open-cut moire copper prohibition is better, the front and rear deviation, left and right deviation are less than 2m, and the left and right dragon ornaments are balanced. An iterative balancing calculation for the openwork moire copper ban is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Off-Limits Mechanical Equilibrium Test of Open-Cut Moire Copper

It can be seen from Figure 4 that the equilibrium force of open-cut moire copper gradually decreases when the applied force increases. However, the change of balance force is a straight line, indicating that the whole of the open-cut moire copper forbidden is in a balanced state, which verifies its stability, and also proves that its dragon pattern decoration does not affect its overall balance, indicating the exquisite manufacturing process of the late Chu State. At present, the Chu bronze is now in the Henan Museum, so that people can go directly to the scene to see it, or through the video and related pictures on the Internet to enjoy this rare bronze unearthed in the Chu State, and in the whole process of appreciation, people can also feel the strange magnificence of its shape and decoration, the exquisite casting technique, and understand the beauty of the bronze unearthed in the Chu State, and then get a happy mood, relax their own experience, so that the viewer is deeply happy to promote its mental health development.

The Structure Meets the Inner Needs of People

In the concept of art healing, it is believed that the satisfaction of people's deep inner dialogue needs is also a kind of art healing. When viewers stand in the museum to watch the bronzes unearthed in the Chu State, they are often alone, quietly appreciating and viewing these ancient bronzes, and observing and interpreting all aspects of these Chu bronzes. For example, they may understand the overall shape of a bronze unearthed in a Chu country, the casting technology used, the specific height, length and width, etc., and may even make an artistic analysis of the bronze unearthed in the Chu State through observation and appreciation, such as silently appreciating its artistic expression and the uniqueness of its shape in their hearts. Because no one disturbs the whole process, this will make them always have a feeling that they are in direct dialogue with the Chu bronze, at this time, the viewer is likely to have the feeling of blending in, slowly being moved and touched, and further, they are likely to have an aesthetic resonance that breaks through the limitations of time and space, and gradually solve their inner thoughts and emotions. Once the viewer has such feelings, it means that they can feel a deep self from this process, so as to overcome the previous psychological barriers and obtain a certain sense of healing.

For example, low self-esteem is often one of the culprits of people's psychological problems, so stimulating a person's self-confidence will have a positive psychological healing effect on people. In order to stimulate a person's self-confidence and change his psychological state of excessive inferiority, it is necessary to first produce a "dialogue" between people and art, and use the positive symbolic elements of art itself to "wake up" the viewer, so as to achieve the healing effect of art is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Cooking Utensils from the Late Chu State

Figure 5 shows the cooking utensil of the late Chu state, the capacity of the cookware is between 15~20L, and the overall shape is wide. How bronze can be made into such a large vessel has always been the focus of research, so electron microscopy scans of different bronze fragments are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Electron Microscopy Scanning Results of Bronze Fragments

Using electron microscopy scanning, it was found that the bronzes of the late Chu state contained a large amount of brass and iron oxide substances, and the molecular distance between the bronze materials was short, about 49.1nm. This result shows that the bronzes of the late Chu state contain alloys such as brass and iron, which increases the pressure resistance of the vessels. The tough Chu bronzes exhibit a wide, symmetrical structure that has a subtle impact on the viewer. Tough materials can add more decorative structures, such as dragons, phoenixes, unicorns, etc., while "dragons", "unicorns" and other beasts symbolize auspicious and wishful thinking, and will also produce certain psychological hints to the viewer. This psychological suggestive effect will allow him

to have a sense of "dialogue" through a deeper tasting of the ding, in the process, the viewer is likely to think that in the bronzes unearthed in the Chu State, dragon patterns and dragon elements have become a feature, and the dragon patterns carved in the bronzes unearthed in the Chu State are often complex and magnificent, and carry a soaring and jumping momentum, or a meandering swimming trend, and the style is often fresh and lively. In addition, in Chinese culture, dragons often have the spiritual meaning of "positive and enterprising", so viewers will think of some positive endogenous forces, such as "dragon soaring tiger leaping", "flying dragon in the sky" and other spiritual forces rich in the meaning of Chinese dragon culture, thus bringing it a spiritual, vigorous and unyielding psychological healing power. In this way, the self-confidence of the viewer can be stimulated and a certain artistic healing effect can be achieved.

ANALYSIS OF THE VALUE OF INSTALLATION ART OF BRONZES UNEARTHED IN THE STATE OF CHU

Enhance the Ecological Reflection Value of Installation Artworks

In the early days, installation art often recreated and redefined man-made products, and many installation artists liked to appropriate industrial objects to express a subconscious anti-industrial tendency, so that installation art has had the expressive function of ecological reflection since its birth. In the second half of the 20th century, many artists began to awaken to environmental awareness, and during this period many installations with nature, ecology and energy as the theme emerged. At present, with the gradual severity of environmental and ecological problems, especially the occurrence of various floods and natural disasters, the public has begun to have a certain sense of ecological reflection, so that the sober people in installation art begin to tend to create works with ecological protection orientation, and are keen to use a global perspective to carry out the design. Bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu are one of the treasures of Chu culture, with strong characteristics of Chu culture, and have unique casting technology and aesthetic value, and bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu have many detailed characteristics in addition to unique shapes and diverse ornaments, including its many different ornaments, often with dragons, Pixiu, flowers and other typical ornaments with different beautiful meanings. In Chinese culture, "dragon" means "auspicious", and for Chinese, the meaning of "auspicious" is often closely related to the context of "nature" and "harmony", so this can be linked to the ecological reflective expression function of the aforementioned installation art. At the same time, in Chinese culture, Pixiu also has the meaning of "harmony" and "prosperity", so this can also be in line with the ecological reflective expression function in installation art. In addition, flowers, tai chi and other ornaments commonly found in bronzes unearthed in the Chu State can also fit the concept of ecological harmony from different angles. Therefore, installation designers or creators can use a variety of bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu with different ornamental characteristics to better combine and construct installation artworks, so that the bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu can be deeply integrated with them. In this way, it can be presented to the public, and then strengthen the public's publicity on ecological environmental protection, and promote their ecological reflection awareness, so as to enhance the ecological reflection function of installation art and help ecological protection publicity.

Enhance the Interactivity of Installation Art

After a period of development, installation art has formed more forms, among which interactive installation art has been more and more used and is well recognized. In interactive installation art, digital information technology has been greatly applied, and common interactive installation art works are often presented together with multimedia technology related to information input or output software and hardware, auxiliary comprehensive materials, therefore, interactive installation art obviously has scientific and technological characteristics, and pays more attention to interaction and innovation. However, simply mastering the relevant multimedia technology is still not enough, in order to improve the value of interactive installation art, the creator must integrate a certain artistic aesthetic connotation for it, and be able to impress people as much as possible in the display process, that is, must have a certain artistic innovation ability, at the same time, but also be able to use a relatively novel and harmonious way, the artistry, special philosophy and cognition contained in it, present, and then trigger people's thinking about the values of the work. Of course, in order to achieve this goal, the creator must strive to improve the interactivity of the work, because any philosophical and unique installation art must be able to make the participants feel that their interactive experience is satisfied. Under the screen display effect, a colorful color is formed, accompanied by pure music with Chu characteristics, which makes people feel gratified by the entire installation art design. When the viewer stops and stops, the shape and structure of the bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu will also make the viewers fall into deep thought, have a beautiful recollection of the bronzes of the State of Chu, and thus get psychological healing.

CONCLUSION

This paper studies the bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu, and finds that the bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu present many categories and characteristics, and have exquisite shapes and various ornaments. Through the structure, ornamentation and structural analysis of bronzes, it is found that Chu bronze means a certain amount of copper and iron, and the structure is symmetrical and balanced, which can provide a basis for the pattern. In the case of complex ornamentation and structural balance, Chu bronzes show extremely high artistic value, can play an artistic healing role, and have high installation art value. However, there are many types of bronzes in the State of Chu, and this paper only selects a few representative bronzes for research, and will increase the types of research in the future, and carry out mechanical simulation analysis to deeply study the archaeological value of the bronzes unearthed in the State of Chu.

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